

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object

Syafa Paper Analysis for Nilai Keluarga Dalam Film Nanti Kita Cerita Tentang Hari Ini

Background and Analysis

Penelitian ini dilakukan dengan tujuan untuk mengetahui nilai keluarga yang terdapat dalam film NKCTHI berawal dari sebuah novel berjudul sama yang ditulis Marcella FP lalu diangkat menjadi suatu web series dan kemudian barulah menjadi film sukses sekaligus film ke tiga belas yang disutradarai oleh Angga Dwimas Sasongko dan diproduksi Anggia Kharisma dengan mengangkat isu drama keluarga film yang tayang pada awal tahun 2020 ini sukses dengan penonton lebih dari dua juta orang sehingga menjadi film Indonesia terlaris pertama di sepanjang tahun 2020 karena ceritanya dekat dengan kehidupan sehari-hari banyak sekali nilai yang dapat diambil salah satunya nilai keluarga. Film NKCTHI juga berhasil merefleksikan beberapa fungsi keluarga menurut BBKN.

Nilai-nilai keluarga dalam film NKCTHI secara umum, ditampilkan secara jelas melalui narasi, kata, maupun dialog film yang bersifat verbal seperti alur cerita, perilaku dan tindakan, serta dialog yang dilakukan para pemeran. Sedangkan secara konotatif, representasi nilai keluarga merupakan pengembangan pemikiran setiap penonton dari makna umumnya. Penggunaan tanda non-verbal seperti mimik dan gestur pemeran, background, teknik pencahayaan dan teknik kamera juga berperan sebagai unsur pendukung pemaknaan nilai keluarga, merujuk pada pengendalian emosi, psikologis, cara pandang dan berpikir setiap penontonnya. Film Nanti Kita Cerita Tentang Hari Ini berhasil merefleksikan makna nilai dan fungsi keluarga yang ada dan berlaku di masyarakat karena dibantu oleh konflik yang nyata, dekat, dan lekat.

Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

- 1) Is it Available data or information to answer it
Iya tersedia data ataupun informasi terkait nilai-nilai keluarga dalam sebuah film terutama film nanti kita cerita tentang hari ini.

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- 2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests
Iya, data didapatkan melalui observasi setiap adegan yang tersaji dalam film nanti
Nanti Kita Cerita Tentang Hari Ini dan beberapa artikel lainnya sebagai pendukung dari data tersebut.
- 3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts)
Pendapat saya, penelitian ini sudah memenuhi persyaratan.
- 4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science
Tidak, karena penelitian ini cenderung berkontribusi ke arah ilmu social.
- 5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening
Pendapat saya iya, karena persoalan keluarga akhir-akhir ini banyak diangkat dan sering kali dikaitkan dengan kesehatan mental.
- 6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and
Iya, permasalahan ini cukup penting sehingga memerlukan jawaban dan solusi secepat mungkin.
- 7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.
Pendapat saya tidak sesuai dengan kemampuan peneliti pada bidang studi yang dipilih.
- 8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred.
Orang-orang sudah cukup paham apa itu arti keluarga dan pentingnya menjalankan nilai-nilai keluarga.
- 9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?
Meningkatkan pengetahuan orang tua, anak, dan seluruh anggota keluarga tentang keluarga dan nilai didalamnya.

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